

Economic Value Added (EVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Economic Value Added (EVA) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the EVA ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the EVA ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the EVA ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 679 journal publications regarding the EVA ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the EVA ratio are divided into 3 clusters and 136 topic items; based on the mapping of Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 34 topics around the influence of the EVA ratio and 30 topics about the determinants of the EVA ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around EVA ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Economic Value Added (EVA); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Economic Value Added (EVA) is a tool that can be used to measure the added value created by a company after considering the cost of capital. The EVA concept was introduced by Stern Stewart & Co., a management consulting company in the 1980s (Arif & Hanifa, 2017). EVA can be calculated by subtracting the cost of capital from a company's operating profit, and then multiplying it by the capital invested in the company. The result is the added value created by the company during a certain period. Banking companies can use EVA to measure their financial performance more accurately (Kurniawati, 2016).

In the banking industry, EVA can provide a more comprehensive view of a bank's financial performance, because the EVA measurement considers the capital costs incurred by the bank. In the banking industry, the cost of capital consists of share capital and debt. By considering the cost of capital in calculating added value, EVA can provide a more accurate view of whether the bank has created sufficient added value for shareholders and creditors (Azlina, 2017). Although the use of EVA in banking is not as popular as in other industries, several large banks in the world have adopted EVA as a tool to measure their financial performance. Some of these large banks include Bank of America, Citigroup, JP Morgan Chase, and several other large banks. However, the use of EVA in banking also has limitations. One of these limitations is EVA measurement which requires accurate and up-to-date data. Banks must have adequate systems and procedures to collect data and carry out EVA calculations accurately (Elfia, 2021). Apart from that, calculating capital costs which are complex and require precise estimates can also be a challenge for banks in using EVA. Nevertheless, the use of EVA in banking continues to grow because EVA can provide a more accurate and comprehensive view of a bank's financial performance. By using EVA, banks can measure how effectively they manage their assets and capital costs, and assist banks in making strategic decisions (Hasanah, 2018).

Research on EVA in banking continues to develop along with increasing interest in the use of EVA as a tool for measuring bank financial performance. Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of using EVA in banking, as well as to study the factors that influence EVA in banking. First, research evaluating the effect of EVA on bank financial performance. The research results show that EVA has a positive and significant influence on bank financial performance. Apart from that, this study also shows that banks that are more effective in managing risk and generating higher profits tend to have greater EVA values (Arsita, 2021). Second, research that evaluates the effect of EVA on the market value of bank shares. The research results show that EVA has a positive and significant influence on the market value of bank shares. This shows that investors tend to give higher value to banks that have greater EVA (Sabirin, 2021). Third, several studies also evaluate the factors that influence EVA in banking in Jordan. The research results show that asset quality, liquidity and leverage have a significant influence on EVA in banks in Jordan (Nurlaila, 2022). Overall, research on the use of EVA in banking shows that EVA can be used as an effective tool for measuring bank financial performance. Apart from that, research also shows that factors such as asset quality, liquidity and leverage can influence the EVA value in banking. However, further research is still needed to understand in more depth the use of EVA in banking and the factors that influence EVA in banking.

VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Mapping Research Topics using Library Research to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding EVA. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research EVA. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the EVA ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Library Research

Economic Value Added (EVA) or Economic Value Added is a concept used to measure the performance of a company by calculating the added value produced by the company after considering the capital costs incurred. In the banking context, EVA is used to measure the added value generated by a bank by comparing the capital costs incurred by the bank with the profits generated (Zannati & Wardoyo, 2016). In this case, the cost of capital includes the cost of borrowing and capital invested by shareholders. If the profit generated by a bank is greater than the capital costs incurred, then the bank is considered to produce positive economic added value. On the other hand, if the profit generated is less than the cost of capital, then the bank is considered inefficient and unable to produce positive economic added value. EVA can help bank management to evaluate company performance and identify areas that need to be improved to increase the company's economic added value (Fitriyah, 2014).

Bibliometric studies are a research method that uses bibliographic and bibliometric analysis techniques to study and analyze the characteristics, trends and patterns of scientific publications in a particular field or scientific discipline. In bibliometric studies, the data used is bibliographic data, namely data regarding scientific publications such as books, journal articles, etc. Bibliographic data is then analyzed using bibliometric techniques such as citation analysis, co-classification analysis, and factor analysis which can produce information about the productivity, quality, and influence of scientific publications in a field. Bibliometric studies can be used for various purposes, such as measuring the influence of a scientific publication, identifying research trends and patterns in a field, and to obtain information about the productivity and quality of publications from a researcher or

research institution. Bibliometric studies are often used in scientific research, policy development, and evaluation of research and teaching programs (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is software used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data. VOSviewer was developed by the Leiden University Centre for Science and Technology Studies and is freely available for use by the public. VOSviewer can be used to analyze and visualize author networks, citation networks, and keyword networks in scientific publications. VOSviewer can also be used to visualize the diversity of topics within a particular research area and can help identify collaborations between researchers and research groups. VOSviewer works by processing bibliographic data imported from databases such as Scopus or Web of Science, and then generating visual maps that show the relationships between data elements. These visual maps can be customized and analyzed with various statistical and bibliometric methods. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, librarians, and other information professionals to generate new information and insights about trends and patterns in scientific research. VOSviewer can also help increase efficiency in research, analysis and management of bibliometric data (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a research method that is carried out by reviewing and analyzing various literature or sources of information related to the topic or research problem you want to research. Library Researchs are conducted to gain a better understanding of a research topic or problem, identify research gaps or debates in the field, and to identify relevant research methods and approaches. In a Library Research study, the sources of information used can be books, journals, conference papers, etc other documents relevant to the research topic or problem. These sources of information are then analyzed and synthesized to prepare summaries and conclusions related to the research topic or problem. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research can be conducted as independent research or as part of wider research. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research can be used for various purposes, such as to develop a theoretical framework, formulate hypotheses, or to evaluate the results of previous research. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research can be carried out using various methods, such as systematic approach, narrative approach, or meta-analysis approach. The approach chosen depends on the objectives and sources of information used (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The research object is Economic Value Added (EVA). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on EVA in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words “Economic Value Added” and “EVA” within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding EVA using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) map the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around EVA using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities)

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around EVA.

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

The VOSViewer software visualization regarding the research development map regarding the EVA ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 3 clusters and 136 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 66 topic items, namely: analytical method, asset, bei, book value, Indonesian stock exchange, cash flow, company value, criteria, data analysis technique, debt, der, earnings per share, effect, eps, equity ratio, f test, firm value, food, stock price, hypothesis testing, idx, impact, independent variable, Indonesian stock exchange, influence, investment, leverage, manufacturing company, multiple linear regression, net profit margin, npm, influence of economic value, influence of return, population, positive effect, price, profitability, purposive sampling method/technique, ratio, relationship, researcher, stock return, roa, roe, roi, sampling technique, share, significant effect/influence/negative effect/positive effect/return, spss, stock exchange/price/return, t test.
- Cluster 2, consists of 66 topic items, namely: economic value added analysis, analysis technique, appoarch, assessment, bank, calculation, capital, comparison, concept, condition, cost, covid, data collection technique, decision, difference, documentation, economic value added, eva method/value, factor, financial performance, financial ratio analysis, financial report/statement/value added, form, fva, good financial performance, income statement, increase, invested capital, investor, quantitative, level, management, measurement, mva value, negative eva value, net operating profit, performance assessment, performance, company, positive eva value/result/value, process, profitability ratio, quantitative approach/data/method, research method, secondary data, share price, shareholder, tax, tbk, wacc.
- Cluster 3, consists of 4 topic items, namely: Indonesian effects, market value, market value added, company.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Economic Value Added (EVA) on Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 34 influences of EVA on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Operating cash flow. The influence of EVA on operating cash flow in banking depends on how bank management uses EVA as a performance measurement tool. If bank management uses EVA to identify investment projects that generate added value, it is likely that the bank will experience positive operating cash flow. However, if the bank only focuses on increasing EVA without paying attention to operating cash flow, the bank may experience liquidity difficulties.

(2) Capital gains. The effect of EVA on capital gains in banking can vary depending on stock market conditions and investor confidence. If investors see the bank's EVA increasing, it is likely that the bank's share price will also increase, so that investors can experience capital gains. However, if stock market conditions are bad or investors do not believe in the EVA method, then the effect of EVA on capital gains can be limited.

(3) Financial Value Added/FVA. FVA is a method of measuring financial performance that is similar to EVA, but FVA takes into account all capital costs incurred by the company. The effect of EVA on FVA in banking can vary depending

on how bank management uses these two methods. If bank management uses these two methods to identify investment projects that generate added value, then the bank can increase both EVA and FVA. However, if bank management only focuses on increasing EVA without paying attention to FVA, it is likely that the bank will experience difficulties in creating sustainable added value.

(4) Stock price. If the bank is able to increase its EVA, then this can affect the bank's share price. This is because EVA is considered a positive indicator of company performance. Investors who look for shares that perform well and provide added value to their shareholders tend to buy bank shares that have high EVA. Thus, increasing EVA can cause banking share prices to rise.

(5) Individual stock price index. The individual stock price index is a measure of stock performance consisting of a group of stocks in the same sector. The effect of EVA on individual banking share price indexes depends on how many bank shares are part of the index and how much EVA contribution from each share makes to the index. If bank EVA continues to increase and the contribution of bank shares to the individual share price index is quite large, then this could have a positive influence on the individual banking share price index.

(6) Financial performance. EVA can help bank management evaluate the efficiency of capital use and determine appropriate investment policies. If banks can utilize EVA well and improve their financial performance, then the bank can obtain higher profits and generate added value for its shareholders. However, if the bank cannot utilize EVA properly, the bank may experience a decline in financial performance. Therefore, it is important for bank management to understand the influence of EVA on financial performance and use this method wisely in making investment decisions.

(7) Customer performance. If banks are able to create sustainable added value through EVA, then this can have a positive impact on customer performance. Banks that succeed in creating added value through EVA tend to have good and stable performance, so that customers can benefit in the form of lower interest rates or cheaper transaction costs. Apart from that, banks that have high EVA also tend to have better abilities in providing innovative services and products to customers.

(8) Company performance. EVA is an indicator of company performance that can be used to evaluate the efficiency of capital use and the company's ability to create added value for shareholders. Banks that succeed in increasing their EVA tend to have better and more stable performance compared to banks that are unable to create added value. This can have a positive impact on overall company performance, including in terms of business growth, profitability and operational efficiency.

(9) Shareholder prosperity. EVA can have a positive impact on shareholder prosperity. If the bank succeeds in creating added value through EVA, then shareholders can obtain higher profits from their investment in the bank. In addition, banks that have high EVA tend to have higher share prices and provide capital gains for shareholders. This can increase shareholder prosperity and strengthen investor confidence in the bank.

(10) Investment feasibility. EVA can be used as an indicator of the feasibility of investing in banking. If the bank succeeds in creating added value through positive EVA, then investment in the bank is considered more feasible. Banks that have a high EVA tend to have a higher company value, and this can attract investors to invest in that bank.

(11) Cash dividend policy. Cash dividend policy can be influenced by EVA. If a bank has a high EVA, then the bank tends to have the ability to pay higher dividends to shareholders. Higher cash dividends can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's image, so that it can help the bank increase company value and attract investors' interest in investing in the bank.

(12) Accounting profit. EVA can have a positive impact on accounting profits in banking. If a bank succeeds in creating added value through EVA, then the bank tends to have better profitability. This can be reflected in higher accounting profits. Apart from that, EVA can also help banks increase operational efficiency and reduce capital costs, so that it can have a positive impact on bank accounting profits.

(13) Operating profit. EVA can have a positive impact on banking operating profits. Banks that succeed in creating added value through EVA tend to have higher profitability. This can strengthen the bank's financial performance, increase revenue and operating profits, and provide profits for shareholders.

(14) Market Value Added/MVA. EVA can also affect MVA in banking. MVA is the difference between the company's market value and the total capital invested in the company. If a bank has a high EVA, then this can increase the MVA of the company. This is because EVA can increase the efficiency of capital use and the company's ability to create added value, so that it can increase investor confidence and attract investors' interest in investing in the company.

(15) Company Market Value. EVA can also affect a company's Market Value in banking. The company's market value is the market value of all shares outstanding in the company. If a bank has a high EVA, then this can increase the company's Market Value. This is because EVA can provide an indication of the company's ability to create added value for shareholders, so that it can increase investor confidence and strengthen the company's image in the eyes of the public.

(16) The value of the company. EVA can affect company value in banking. If the bank succeeds in creating added value through positive EVA, then this can increase the value of the company. This is because EVA can show the company's ability to create added value for shareholders, so that it can increase investor confidence and attract investors' interest in investing in the bank.

(17) Equal distribution of income. EVA can have a positive impact on income distribution in banking. Banks that have high EVA tend to have higher company value and are able to provide greater profits for shareholders. This can provide economic benefits to shareholders which can improve income distribution.

(18) Sustainability report disclosure. EVA can influence the disclosure of sustainability reports in banks. Banks that have high EVA tend to have focus on creating long-term added value for shareholders, which can also include social and environmental responsibility. This can encourage banks to be more active in disclosing sustainability reports, which will increase bank transparency and strengthen the bank's image in the eyes of the public. Disclosure of sustainability reports can also increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's position in the market.

(19) Failure Predictors. EVA can affect company value in banking. If the bank succeeds in creating added value through positive EVA, then this can increase the value of the company. This is because EVA can show the company's ability to create added value for shareholders, so that it can increase investor confidence and attract investors' interest in investing in the bank.

(20) Price to Book Value/PBV. EVA can have a positive impact on income distribution in banking. Banks that have high EVA tend to have higher company value and are able to provide greater profits for shareholders. This can provide economic benefits to shareholders which can improve income distribution.

(21) Valuation of company equity. EVA can affect the disclosure of Sustainability Reports in banking. Banks that have high EVA tend to focus on creating long-term added value for shareholders, which can also include social and environmental responsibility. This can encourage banks to be more active in disclosing Sustainability Reports, which will increase bank transparency and strengthen the bank's image in the eyes of the public. Disclosure of the Sustainability

Report can also increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's position in the market.

(22) Optimal portfolio. EVA can influence the optimal portfolio in banking. An optimal portfolio is a combination of investments in various financial instruments that provide maximum returns with minimum risk. Banks that have high EVA can show better financial performance and better ability to manage risk. This can increase the bank's credibility and reputation, thereby enabling the bank to gain access to capital and gain recognition as a credible financial institution, thereby improving its optimal portfolio.

(23) Financial ratios. EVA can also affect financial ratios in banking. Financial ratios are a measure of a bank's financial performance which can be measured through a comparison between two related elements in the financial statements. Banks that have high EVA tend to have better financial ratios. EVA can provide an indication of a bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance, so that it can improve financial ratios such as profitability ratios and efficiency ratios.

(24) Return On Assets/ROA. EVA can also affect Return On Assets (ROA) in banking. ROA is a measure of a bank's effectiveness in using assets to generate profits. Banks that have high EVA tend to have higher ROA. This is because EVA can provide an indication of the bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance, so that it can increase the effectiveness of using bank assets and increase ROA.

(25) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a measure of a bank's efficiency in generating profits using its own capital. EVA can influence ROE in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have higher ROE. EVA can provide an indication of a bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance, thereby increasing the efficiency of using the bank's own capital and increasing ROE.

(26) Return On Investment/ROI. ROI is a measure of a bank's effectiveness in using overall capital, both own capital and loan capital, to generate profits. EVA can affect ROI in banking, where banks having a high EVA tends to have a higher ROI. EVA can provide an indication of a bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance, thereby increasing the overall effectiveness of using bank capital and increasing ROI.

(27) returns. Stock Return is a measure of the profits received by bank shareholders on their investment. EVA can influence stock returns in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to provide higher stock returns. EVA can provide an indication of a bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance, so that it can provide confidence for investors and increase stock returns.

(28) Shareholder Value. Shareholder Value is a measure of the added value received by bank shareholders. EVA can influence Shareholder Value in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to provide greater added value for shareholders. By having a high EVA, banks can provide greater profits for shareholders in the long term and increase shareholder value.

(29) Optimal capital structure. Optimal Capital Structure is the optimal capital composition that can provide the greatest profits for the bank and shareholders. EVA can influence the Optimal Capital Structure in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have an optimal capital structure. By having a high EVA, banks can obtain capital at lower costs, thereby increasing profits and achieving an optimal capital structure.

(30) Company size. Company size can influence a bank's ability to create added value and improve financial performance. EVA can influence company size in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have faster growth and can increase the size of their company. By having a high EVA, banks can gain investor

trust and allocate capital for business expansion which can increase the size of the company.

(31) Stock return rate. Return on Equity measures the company's ability to generate profits for shareholders. EVA can influence the rate of return on shares in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have a higher rate of return on shares. This is because EVA can increase the added value obtained by the bank, thereby providing greater profits for shareholders.

(32) Tobin Q. Tobin Q is the ratio between a company's market value and its book value. EVA can influence Tobin Q in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have higher Tobin Q. This is because EVA can influence the added value received by the company, thereby increasing the company's market value.

(33) Stock valuation. Stock Valuation measures the intrinsic value of a company's shares. EVA can influence stock valuations in banks, where banks that have high EVA tend to have higher stock valuations. This is because EVA can increase the added value obtained by the company, thereby increasing the intrinsic value of the company's shares.

(34) Stock trading volume. Stock Trading Volume measures the number of shares traded in a certain period. EVA can influence Stock Trading Volume in banking, where banks that have high EVA tend to have higher Stock Trading Volume. This is because EVA can increase investor confidence in the company and increase share liquidity, thereby increasing share trading volume.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Determinant Variables of Economic Value Added/EVA in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 30 EVA determinant variables in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Acquisition. Acquisitions can have a significant impact on EVA in banking. Properly executed acquisitions can increase the scale of a bank's operations and enable the bank to achieve synergy between the acquired business and the bank's core business. This can increase bank income and improve operational efficiency. However, inappropriate or poorly integrated acquisitions can affect EVA in a negative way.

(2) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR Award. Receiving a CSR award can have a positive impact on EVA in banking. The CSR award shows that the bank has carried out socially and environmentally responsible activities, which can improve the bank's image and customer trust. This can help banks earn higher revenues and increase profits, which can ultimately increase EVA.

(3) Corporate Governance. Corporate Governance can have a significant influence on EVA in banking. Good corporate governance can help banks avoid unnecessary risks and increase operational efficiency. This can help banks to achieve better financial results and in turn increase EVA. However, poor or ineffective corporate governance can result in higher risks and reduce the bank's financial performance, thereby reducing EVA.

(4) Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on banking EVA worldwide. Covid-19 affects the entire economic sector, including the banking sector, by reducing economic growth, increasing credit risk, and decreasing loan demand. The Covid-19 pandemic has also changed consumer and business behavior, forcing banks to adapt quickly to face new challenges. Therefore, Covid-19 may significantly affect bank EVA.

(5) Debt Equity Ratio/DER. DER or debt equity ratio measures the use of debt and own capital by banks. A low DER indicates a lower level of risk and provides greater flexibility in dealing with uncertain circumstances. On the other hand, a high DER indicates greater risk and can negatively affect a bank's financial performance, including EVA.

(6) Asset efficiency. Asset efficiency is a measure of how efficiently banks use assets to generate income. The higher the asset efficiency, the better the bank can manage its assets and maximize income. This may contribute to increased EVA. However, low asset efficiency can reduce income and cause a decrease in EVA.

(7) Intellectual Capital. Intellectual Capital includes knowledge, experience and skills possessed by employees, as well as intellectual property rights such as patents, trademarks and copyrights. Strong Intellectual Capital can increase operational efficiency, innovation and banking ability to create added value for customers. This can increase revenue and ultimately increase banking EVA.

(8) Asset investment. Asset Investments include investments in assets that can generate income, such as investments in shares, bonds and property. Good asset investment can increase banking income and optimize capital use. However, inappropriate asset investment can pose risks and negatively affect the bank's financial performance, including EVA.

(9) Initial Public Offering/IPO. An IPO can give banks access to a larger source of funds to expand their business and increase growth. This can increase revenue and ultimately increase banking EVA. However, IPOs can also result in high costs and increase pressure to produce good financial performance, which can affect EVA.

(10) Dividend policy. If a company chooses to pay higher dividends, this may reduce the amount of funds available for reinvestment in the business. However, if a company chooses to maintain profits and strengthen its equity, this can increase the company's ability to invest in profitable projects. So, the right dividend policy can influence banking EVA.

(11) Debt policy. Debt policy reflects the proportion of funds a company obtains from debt to its equity capital. Debt can increase a company's profit potential, but it can also increase the risk of bankruptcy. If the company uses debt appropriately and effectively, this can increase EVA. However, if the company uses debt unwisely and is unable to meet its debt obligations, this can cause a decrease in EVA.

(12) Company diversification policy. A company's diversification policy is a strategy to expand a company's products or services into different markets to reduce risk. However, diversification can also affect EVA. If diversification is carried out correctly, it can increase company growth and increase added value for shareholders. However, if diversification is carried out ineffectively and does not take into account the company's core expertise, this can reduce EVA.

(13) Managerial ownership. Managerial ownership reflects the proportion of shares owned by company managers. If managers own a significant stake in the company, this can motivate them to make decisions that benefit the company in the long term, including investment and financing decisions that impact EVA. However, if managers focus only on their personal interests, this can reduce EVA.

(14) Funding decisions. Funding decisions reflect the sources of funds used by the company to finance operational or investment activities. The right funding decisions can increase EVA by reducing the company's cost of capital or increasing returns on invested capital. However, if a company uses expensive sources of funds or borrows too much, this can increase the cost of capital and reduce EVA.

(15) Investation decision. Investment decisions reflect the allocation of company funds to investment projects. The right investment decisions can increase EVA by increasing returns on invested capital and increasing company growth. However, if the company makes investments that are unproductive or do not match the company's core expertise, this can reduce EVA.

(16) Dividend decision. Dividend decisions can influence EVA in banking. If a bank decides to pay high dividends, it can reduce the amount of funds available to invest in projects that generate higher EVA. On the other hand, if the bank chooses to retain most of the profits as retained earnings, the bank can use these funds to develop the business and increase EVA.

(17) Leverage. Leverage or debt to equity ratio can affect EVA in banking. If a bank has high leverage, then the bank will pay higher interest on its debt. This can reduce the profits available to invest in projects that generate higher EVA. However, if the leverage used is effective and used to fund projects that produce EVA that is higher than the cost of debt, then leverage can increase EVA.

(18) Company merger. Mergers or mergers of companies can affect EVA in banking. If a bank merges with another bank that has projects that produce higher EVA, then this can increase the EVA of the merged bank. However, mergers can also increase the operational and administrative costs of the merging banks, which can reduce EVA.

(19) Asset management. Good asset management can increase EVA in banking. Banks that can maximize the use of their assets to generate high income can increase their EVA. For example, if a bank can improve its credit quality by reducing the risk of not-so-good credit, the bank can earn higher income from the interest paid by borrowers. Apart from that, good asset management can also increase bank efficiency in managing its assets and reduce operational costs.

(20) Liability management. Good liability management can also increase EVA in banking. Banks that can minimize their capital costs by managing their liabilities well can increase their EVA. For example, if a bank can issue bonds at a lower interest rate than other banks, then the bank can reduce its cost of capital and increase its profits. Apart from that, good liability management can also help banks manage liquidity risk and achieve liquidity targets.

(21) Liability asset management. Good asset-liability management (ALM) can also increase EVA in banking. ALM is a risk management process carried out by banks by considering the influence of risk on the bank's assets and liabilities. By paying attention to the assets and liabilities side simultaneously, banks can optimize the use of funds and minimize risks associated with fluctuations in interest rates and exchange rates. Thus, banks can increase income and reduce capital costs, which can increase EVA.

(22) Moderation of family ownership. Family ownership in banking can influence EVA, depending on how much influence the family has in decision making at the bank. Studies show that greater family ownership tends to result in lower EVA, because large family ownership can reduce management effectiveness and hinder rational and independent decision making. However, this negative effect can be reduced if the family provides support to bank management and has goals that are in line with company goals.

(23) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a financial ratio that measures a company's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. High ROA can increase EVA in banking. Banks that can maximize the use of their assets to generate high income and reduce operational costs can increase their ROA and EVA.

(24) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a financial ratio that measures a company's ability to generate profits from shareholder equity. A high ROE can increase EVA in banking. Banks that can increase the efficiency of using capital, increase income and reduce operational costs can increase their ROE and EVA.

(25) Capital structure. The right capital structure can influence EVA in banking. An optimal capital structure can increase profits and reduce capital costs. Banks that have the right capital structure can increase company value, so that EVA increases. However, an inappropriate capital structure, such as too much debt, can increase the risk of bankruptcy and reduce EVA.

(26) Ownership structure. A good ownership structure can influence EVA in banking. Banks that have a good and stable ownership structure tend to have stable management, are consistent in making decisions, and can build long-term relationships with customers. This can improve bank performance and its EVA.

However, an ownership structure that is unstable or too concentrated in one shareholder can increase the risk of irrational decision making and reduce EVA.

(27) Debt ratio. The debt ratio can affect EVA in banking. The right debt ratio can increase EVA, because it can increase the use of capital and increase profit potential. However, too much debt can increase risk of bankruptcy and lower EVA. Therefore, it is important to consider the right debt ratio to maximize EVA in banking.

(28) Restructurisation. Restructuring can influence EVA in banking by increasing productivity, reducing costs, and increasing profitability. In some cases, restructuring can increase a company's value and its EVA. However, restructuring can also require significant costs, so a comprehensive analysis needs to be carried out to ensure that the restructuring can increase EVA in banking.

(29) Total Assets Turnover/TATO. TATO can influence EVA in banking by increasing income and asset use. Banks that have high TATO tend to have higher profits and higher company value, so that their EVA increases. However, keep in mind that a high TATO can pose higher risks, such as credit risk and operational risk.

(30) Company size. Company size can influence EVA in banking. Larger companies tend to have more resources and can benefit from economies of scale and greater market power. However, companies that are too large can also experience complex management problems and require high costs for risk control. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out careful analysis to determine the optimal company size in order to maximize EVA in banking.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of research publications regarding the Economic Value Added (EVA) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 1996 Until 2023, originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there will be 679 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the EVA ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 3 clusters and 136 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 66 topics, cluster 2 consists of 66 topics, and cluster 3 consists of 4 topics. Third, based on mapping Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 34 topics related to the influence of the EVA ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: operating cash flow, capital gains, Financial Value Added/FVA, stock prices, individual stock price index, financial performance, performance customers, company performance, shareholder prosperity, investment feasibility, cash dividend policy, accounting profit, operating profit, Market Value Added/MVA, company Market Value, company value, equity income, sustainability report disclosure, Bank Failure Predictor, Price to Book Value/PBV, company equity assessment, optimal portfolio, financial ratios, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, stock returns, Shareholder Value, optimal capital structure, company size, stock return rate, Tobin Q, stock valuation and stock trading volume. And there are 30 topics related to the determinants of the EVA ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: acquisitions, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR Award, Corporate Governance, Covid-19, Debt Equity Ratio/DER, asset efficiency, Intellectual Capital, asset investment, Initial Public Offering/IPO, dividend policy, debt policy, policy, corporate diversification, managerial ownership, funding decisions, investment decisions, dividend decisions, leverage, corporate mergers, asset management, liability management, management assets liabilities, family ownership moderation, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, capital structure, ownership structure, ratio debt, restructuring, Total Assets Turnover/TATO, and company size.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span of research data. So that the following research results can be obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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